

The new academic year brings a sense of excitement for all of us in the DDI community. Read more to find out about interesting events related to DDI and new developments in the growing area of DDI-compatible software.

Mary Vardigan, Director, DDI Alliance

Second Annual European DDI Users Meeting to Take Place in The Hague

The [2nd Annual European DDI Users Group \(EDDI\) Meeting](#) is scheduled to take place in The Hague, Netherlands, on December 8 - 9. This second EDDI meeting follows a successful [first meeting](#), which was hosted by the IDSC of IZA in Bonn, Germany, in December 2009.

EDDI 2010 is organized jointly by [CentERdata](#) - Institute for Data Collection and Research; [DANS](#) - Data Archiving and Networked Services; [GESIS](#) - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences; [IZA](#) - Institute for the Study of Labor; [SURF](#) - the collaborative organization for IT innovations in higher education in the Netherlands; and [Library and IT Services of Tilburg University](#).

EDDI 2010 will feature a plenary presentation by [Herbert Van de Sompel](#), Lead of the Digital Library Research and Prototyping Team of the [Los Alamos National Laboratory Research Library](#). Training on DDI 3 will also be offered.

[Paper submissions](#) are now being accepted through September 12.

DDI Developers Group to Convene Before EDDI

A meeting for tools developers and implementers will take place just before the EDDI meeting in The Hague on December 6 - 8, Monday, Tuesday, and Wednesday morning. Agenda topics will include interoperability, open source tools, promoting DDI tools, sharing experiences, and future collaboration.

DDI Technical Committee to Meet in Minneapolis

During the week of September 20, members of the DDI Technical Implementation Committee (TIC) will meet in Minneapolis to work on the next versions of the DDI specification in the DDI 2 and DDI 3 development lines.

Workshops and Training Offered

Several opportunities to learn more about DDI and related standards are scheduled in coming months.

- [Eurostat SDMX Technical Workshop](#) ~ Prague, September 30 to October 1
- [DDI Expert Workshop](#) on “Managing Metadata for Longitudinal Data – Best Practices” ~ Schloss Dagstuhl, Wadern, Germany, October 18 - 22. There has been a lot of interest in this workshop from longitudinal data producers, and there is now a waiting list for the event.
- [DDI Training](#), “Using DDI 3 to Support Production, Management, Dissemination, and Preservation Systems for Data in the Social Sciences and Economics” ~ Schloss Dagstuhl, Wadern, Germany, October 25 - 29. There are still openings in this training event. Interested participants should send [email inquiries](#) as soon as possible to secure a seat in the training.
- [SDMX Global Conference](#), provisionally scheduled for Washington, DC, May 2 - 4, 2011. Details to be confirmed.

IASSIST Quarterly to Feature DDI in Special Issue

The upcoming issue of the [IASSIST Quarterly](#), to be published later in September, will have a special focus on DDI with the following six articles. Thank you to the authors for making this special issue possible.

- *Metadata-Driven Survey Design* ~ By Jeremy Iverson
- *Questasy: Online Survey Data Dissemination Using DDI 3* ~ By Marika de Bruijne
- *Implementing DDI 3: The German Microcensus Case Study* ~ By Andias Wira-Alam and Oliver Hopt
- *Metadata Creation, Transformation and Discovery for Social Science Data Management: The DAMES Project Infrastructure* ~ By Jesse M. Blum, Guy C. Warner, Simon B. Jones, Paul S. Lambert, Alison S. F. Dawson, Koon Leai Larry Tan, and Kenneth J. Turner
- *Building a Modular DDI 3 Editor* ~ By Jannik Jensen and Dan Kristiansen
- *Controlled Vocabularies for DDI 3: Enhancing Machine-Actionability* ~ By Taina Jääskeläinen, Meinhard Moschner, and Joachim Wackerow

[Wales Local Government Data Unit](#), which uses Nesstar to disseminate data in both English and Welsh.

Space Time Research Supports DDI and SDMX

[Space Time Research](#) in Australia has announced that its popular [SuperSTAR](#) tabulation and dissemination software will be adding support for the [Statistical Data and Metadata eXchange \(SDMX\)](#) standard as part of its Release 7.0. SDMX is a global initiative to facilitate the automated exchange and processing of data and metadata between organizations.

A version of SuperSTAR providing large table tabulation and Save-to-SDMX capability from SuperWEB2 is available today. SuperSTAR Release 7.0 including SDMX Web services, DDI 3.1 microdata import support, and other statistical features will be available in mid-2010.

To facilitate involvement from the statistical community in SuperSTAR development plans, Space Time Research has initiated a SuperSTAR SDMX and DDI Data Exchange group. The SuperSTAR SDMX and DDI Data Exchange Group is a forum for interested parties to review and comment on the SuperSTAR SDMX functional design and use cases, and provide other product development input.

You can read more about this initiative on the [project homepage](#) and on the [Space Time Research blog](#).

The DDI Web Site Needs Your Help...

The newly launched DDI Alliance Web site was created by members of the DDI community. We now need your help to maintain and improve it.

The [Drupal](#) content management system underlying the site is easy to use and makes editing the site fairly straightforward. If you are interested in making a contribution by working on the site, please contact the [DDI Director](#).

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Welcome to the DDI

A metadata specification for the social sciences

Use DDI to:

- Document your data across the life cycle
- Interoperate with others
- Do Data Intelligently (DDI)!

Find out how others have put [DDI to work](#) in their organizations, explore [resources](#) for learning more about and using the DDI, or join the [DDI Community](#).

[Download the DDI 3.1 Specification](#)